

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.6: 2nd Network of Interest

WP7 – Dissemination

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D7.6 - 2 nd Network of Interest			
Work Package	WP 7 - Dissemination			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	01 May 2017	Actual	02 May 2017
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	PLANO2			
Responsible Author	Mr. Vassileios Tsekeridis, Ms Ioanna Papaioannou			
Contributions from	Dr. Eleni Hatziyanni, Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis, Dr. (Ms.) Machi Simeonidou, Ms. Maria Vogiatzi, Ms. Ioanna Pavlou, Ms. Roxana Nica			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1	01/06/2016	v1	1 st version of deliverable	Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis, Dr. Machi Simeonidou, Mr. Lazaros Xenidis, Ms. Maria Vogiatzi, Ms. Ioanna Pavlou, Ms. Roxana Nica
2	02/05/2017	Final	Updated deliverable	Mr. Vassileios Tsekeridis, Ms Ioanna Papaioannou, Ms Maria Vogiatzi, Mr Christodoulos Keratidis, Ms Ioanna Pavlou, Mr Grigorios Mygdakos

Disclaimer

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© STEP Consortium, 2015

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	4
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Purpose of the deliverable	5
2.2	Structure and contents of the deliverable	5
2.3	Upcoming Nol deliverables	5
3	STEP Network of Interest	6
3.1	Definition	6
3.2	Methodology of the Nol establishment	6
3.3	STEP Target network categories	6
3.4	Data entry	6
3.5	Targets and Metrics	7
4	Analysis	8
4.1	Group type	8
4.2	Country	9
4.3	EU/Non EU	10
4.4	Type of stakeholder	10
5	Discussion	11
6	Activities performed so far	12
6.1	Online Activities	12
6.2	Offline activities	13
7	Overview of the progress towards the expected results	13
8	Future plans and engagement with the Nol	14
9	Conclusions	14
	ANNEX A – STEP 2 nd Newsletter	15
	ANNEX B – STEP 3 rd Newsletter	16
	ANNEX C – STEP 1 st Webinar	17

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Number of Nol entries per group category as of end of May 2016	8
Figure 2: Number of Nol entries per EU or Non EU countries	10
Figure 3: Number of entries per organisation type	11

1 *Executive summary*

The Deliverable D7.6 “2nd Network of Interest” provides an update of the Deliverable D7.4 “1st Network of Interest”. It describes the work carried out from Month 13 (June 2016) until Month 23 (April 2017) for the further development and maintenance of the STEP Network of Interest (NoI), as well as the future plans for the engagement of the members of the network in STEP.

The STEP NoI is a community of individual persons originating from different types of organisations, who share a common interest relevant to the STEP objectives. These individuals can act as a dissemination pole for other stakeholders, but also have the potential to create the customer base for the future commercialisation of the STEP outcomes. The NoI helps to ensure that the STEP eParticipation platform will be relevant to future possible stakeholders. The dissemination impact indicator for the STEP NoI is 1.000 registered individual stakeholders by the end of the project (Month 30). This target has been achieved since Month 18 (November 2016) and today there are 1095 registered individual stakeholders.

An updated version of this deliverable will be submitted in November 2017 (M30), when the STEP project will come to an end.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the deliverable

The deliverable D7.6 2nd Network of Interest represents the 2nd edition of the D 7.4 1st Network of Interest. This deliverable is submitted 23 months after the beginning of the project and eleven months after the submission of the first version of the deliverable. The present document intends to provide an update on the actions carried out since Month 13 (June 2016) for the maintenance of the existing network, as well as for its further enrichment. Moreover, the deliverable D7.6 describes the future engagement activities that have been scheduled until Month 30 (November 2017), when the project ends.

2.2 Structure and contents of the deliverable

The structure of the deliverable is the following:

Chapter 3 includes a definition of what the STEP NoI is, a brief presentation of the methodology and the different types of group categories that form the NoI. This chapter also includes the projected metrics and targets set in the STEP project DoA and Dissemination plan.

Chapter 4 is dedicated exclusively to the analysis of the NoI entries and the graphical representation of the results.

Chapter 5 includes a short discussion on the analysis of the 2nd version of STEP NoI.

Chapter 6 includes a brief description of all the activities performed so far regarding the NoI.

Chapter 7 includes an overview of the progress towards the target metrics.

Chapter 8 provides information on the future activities for the engagement of the STEP NoI, as well as plans to expand the network. This includes ways to maintain the communication, interaction, and interest of the network.

Chapter 9 briefly presents the conclusions of the present deliverable.

2.3 Upcoming NoI deliverable

The establishment and maintenance of the STEP NoI is an ongoing process that spans throughout the entire lifetime of the STEP project. For that reason a number of deliverables have been/will be prepared for keeping up with the progress of the network development and engagement. These deliverables have been carefully placed in selected time periods that reflect the overall progress of the project. The current deliverable is due on Month 23 (End of April 2017) and it is an update of the deliverable D7.4 1st Network of Interest. The deliverable D7.9 3rd Network of Interest is due on Month 30 (End of November 2017) and will be the final report on the STEP NoI, which will provide information on the activities that will be performed from Month 24 (May 2017) until Month 30 (November 2017).

3 STEP Network of Interest

3.1 Definition

The STEP NoI is a **community of individual persons** who are affiliated with a variety of private companies, governmental and non-governmental organisations at a local, regional and national level, and share a common interest related to the STEP project. The idea behind the NoI is to gather potential stakeholders/users of the platform, to exchange information and thoughts on the STEP eParticipation platform and its components, but also to offer these individuals the opportunity to test the STEP eParticipation platform and provide feedback. The most significant objective of the NoI establishment is to **act as a main dissemination pole for other stakeholders**, but also to create the first customer base for the future commercialisation of the STEP platform.

3.2 Methodology of the NoI establishment

The methodology for the establishment and development of STEP's Network of Interest is described in detail in D7.4 1st Network of Interest (Chapter 3.2 Methodology of the NoI establishment). As it is described in the abovementioned document, STEP's NoI is divided in two groups, a) the **Core Group** which consists of stakeholders who are considered to be of particular interest for STEP and b) the **General Group** which includes the rest of the contacts that may have an interest on the project. An additional category was added in the NoI, under the name "**Newsletter subscribers**". This category is comprised only by the "email" variable, since people who are registered in the Newsletter are asked to provide only their email. However, since they decided to register on their own initiative, we suppose that they are stakeholders and potential users of the STEP tool.

3.3 STEP Target network categories

In order to set the basis for the analysis of the collected contact list of individuals, the categories presented in the previous chapter have been narrowed down and grouped in the following categories: 1) NGOs/Environmental and Youth Organisations, 2) Public Authorities, 3) SMEs/ Private companies, 4) Existing Platforms, 5) University/Institute/Research Centres and 6) Organisers of relevant events. These categories are described in detail at D7.4 1st Network of Interest (Chapter 3.3 STEP Target network categories).

3.4 Data entry

As it is described in D7.4 1st Network of Interest (Chapter 3.4 Data entry) the members of the NoI are listed in a standard spreadsheet software. The following **column variables** were created to assist effective data entry: 1) **Name**, 2) **Email**, 3) **Organisation**, 4) **Type of Stakeholder**, 5) **Country**, 6) **EU/Non EU**, 7) **Group Type**. It was decided that this dataset is sufficient for the analysis, so there was no need to include additional categories.

3.5 Targets and Metrics

The establishment and maintenance of the Noi is a dissemination activity of the STEP project. Therefore it has to be monitored for its progress and effectiveness towards the targets set in the STEP Dissemination Plan. The dissemination impact indicator for the STEP Noi is **1.000 registered individual stakeholders** by the end of the project. The impact indicator was achieved since Month 18 (November 2016). However, since the Noi is quite important for the effective dissemination of STEP, the network will be further enriched until the end of the project and additional members will be added.

4 Analysis

This chapter is dedicated to the analysis of the list of individuals that constitute the STEP NoI. As of the date that the current deliverable was being written (End of April 2017) the NoI list contains **1095 individual entries**.

4.1 Group type

From the total entries of the NoI, 151 members belong into the Core Group, 925 in the General Group and 19 have been subscribed in STEP's newsletter.

Group Type	Number of Entries
Core	151
General	925
Newsletter Subscribers	19
Total	1095

Figure 1: Number of NoI entries per group category as of end of May 2016

4.2 Country

The variable "Country" includes the country that the organisation is based and is active. The number of entries describes the number of individuals registered in the STEP Nol. The category "Newsletter Subscribers" is not included in this analysis, since there are not available data.

Country	Number of Entries	%
Albania	4	0,37
Armenia	21	1,95
Austria	63	5,86
Belgium	189	17,57
Bulgaria	2	0,19
Croatia	19	1,77
Cyprus	17	1,58
Czech Republic	52	4,83
Denmark	6	0,56
Estonia	10	0,93
Finland	31	2,88
France	10	0,93
FYROM	25	2,32
Georgia	2	0,19
Germany	84	7,81
Greece	28	2,60
Hungary	7	0,65
Iceland	1	0,09
Ireland	9	0,84
Italy	37	3,44
Kenya	2	0,19
Korea	1	0,09

Country	Number of Entries	%
Latvia	8	0,74
Lithuania	97	9,01
Luxemburg	24	2,23
Malta	12	1,12
Moldova	1	0,09
Netherlands	14	1,30
Norway	4	0,37
Poland	4	0,37
Portugal	22	2,04
Romania	9	0,84
Russia	7	0,65
Serbia	18	1,67
Slovakia	9	0,84
Slovenia	5	0,46
Spain	88	8,18
Sweden	33	3,07
Switzerland	43	4,00
Turkey	6	0,56
UK	49	4,55
Ukraine	2	0,19
Washington	1	0,09
Total	1076	100

4.3 EU/Non EU

The variable “EU/Non EU” indicates whether the organisation of registered individuals is based in a country that is a member of the European Union or not. The category “Newsletter Subscribers” is not included in this variable analysis, since there are not available data.

EU/ Non EU	Number of Entries	%
EU	936	87
Non EU	140	13
Total	1076	100

Figure 2: Number of Nol entries per EU or Non EU countries

4.4 Type of stakeholder

The variable “Type of stakeholder” describes the type of organisations to which the registered individuals are affiliated. The category “Newsletter Subscribers” is not included in this variable analysis, since there are not available data.

Type of Stakeholder	Number of Entries	%
NGO/ Environmental and Youth Organisations	792	73,6
Platform	58	5,4
Public Authorities	105	9,8
SMEs	9	0,8
University/Institute/Research Center	94	8,7
Miscellaneous	18	1,7
Total	1076	100

Figure 3: Number of entries per organisation type

5 Discussion

Within this chapter a brief discussion on the results generated from the analysis of the 2nd version of the STEP Nol list is presented. To start with, it has to be noted that the partners who were responsible for the compilation of the Nol list and the maintenance of the contacts have put their best effort to identify, locate and engage most of the individual entries of the list. However, even though the initial target of 1.000 members has been achieved and overcome, the development of the Nol is an ongoing procedure that lasts during the whole duration of the STEP project and it will be kept updated and in revision. Throughout the duration of the project, any additional contacts that are added to the partners' networks will be added to the STEP Nol. Furthermore, the STEP project recognition and the dissemination activities will enlarge our network of contacts, and these will be added to the Nol.

Regarding the variable "Group type", the 151 entries of the Core Group represented 14% of the Nol, whereas the General Group with 925 entries represented the 84% of the network. The difference that occurs between these two groups can be attributed to the fact that the individuals who might be interested in the commercialization of the project and are included in the Core Group are far fewer than the rest of the stakeholders.

Regarding the variable "Country", a heterogeneous distribution of entries from 43 different countries is observed. The existence of 189 entries (17,57%) from Belgium is attributed to the fact that many pan-European organisations have their headquarters there.

Regarding the variable "EU/Non EU", the majority of entries (87%) originate from the EU. This is attributed to the fact that STEP is an EU funded project targeting primarily EU audiences but also due to the fact that most project partners come from EU, therefore their stakeholder search is focused on EU.

Finally, regarding the variable "Type of Stakeholder", 792 (73,6 %) entries were from an NGO/Environmental and Youth organisations, while the contacts originated from University/Institute/Research Centers, Public Authorities and Existing Platforms had approximately similar levels of representation in the Nol with 8,7 %, 9,8 % and 5,4 % respectively. The dominance of NGO/Environmental and Youth Organisations entries reflects the importance of these organisations in youth movement in EU and beyond. Also these results denote that,

for the next period, more effort should be made to engage more Public Authorities and relevant initiatives in the STEP Nol.

6 Activities performed so far

6.1 Online Activities

STEP Newsletters

Since June 2016 two newsletters have been prepared and sent to the contact list via a professional mass emailing solution (Mailchimp).

The first one, which was STEP's 2nd Newsletter (Annex A), was sent at the beginning of July 2016 (M14). The topics addressed in this newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP project
- Presentation of STEP's video
- A research conducted by the STEP team on how the social media can be used for the engagement of young people
- Practical suggestions on how public authorities can engage young people in decision making procedures for environmental issues
- A brief presentation of the workshops organized in the framework of STEP
- A brief presentation of the events that the STEP partners have participated
- A brief description of the synergies that the STEP team has tried to establish

The second one was STEP's 3rd Newsletter (Annex B), and it was sent at the beginning of April 2017 (M23). The topics included in this newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP platform
- An introduction of STEP pilots
- Information on the EU pilot concept and the meeting of the STEP team with the Chairwoman of the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee of the European Parliament (ENVI Committee)
- Presentation of the STEP blog
- Information on the 1st STEP Webinar: "Let's talk about e-participation!"
- Information on relevant EU projects and initiatives

STEP 1st Webinar

The first STEP webinar "Let's talk about e-participation" (Annex C), took place on Monday, 14 of March 2017. Three European projects on digital participation, STEP, [EMPATIA](#) and [EUth](#) e-met and presented the work they have accomplished so far and their plans for the future. After the presentations, a lively Q&A session followed and a fruitful discussion took place on how the municipalities can engage young users in decision making, what are the next plans of each project and how such kinds of tools can be effectively promoted. Additionally, the participants had the chance to provide their feedback on STEP and the other too e-participation tools.

An invitation was sent to all the members of the Network of Interest, as well as relevant posts were uploaded in STEP's social media accounts.

All the members of the NoI are able to unsubscribe from the STEP mailing list any time they want. However, only 3 of them asked to be excluded from the list. This is an evidence of the interest of most of the members of the NoI for the STEP project.

6.2 Offline activities

Together with the online activities, the STEP team has participated in a number of events in order to disseminate the project and ensure the dialogue about STEP. During the events, the STEP team had the chance to present the project to stakeholders, as well as to network with youth workers, policy makers, software developers, participation experts and other stakeholders. More specific, these events were:

- #BePart Summit 2016: Berlin, 14-16 November, 2016

#BePart is a 3-day event organized for European e-participation stakeholders and focuses on one basic aim: to bring them all together in order to share good practices and experiences on e-participation and identify the challenges and the opportunities. STEP team was there in order to present the project and the STEP platform to the Summit, interact with other stakeholders and create synergies with youth organizations.

- Thessaloniki Climathon “Inspiring behavioral change for a climate friendly city”: Thessaloniki, 22-23rd October, 2016

Climathon is a 24 hour hackathon event that is being organized in parallel in different cities. In October 2016, Climathon was organized in 59 cities from all over the world. The organisation of Climathon in Thessaloniki was an opportunity to open for the first time a broad discussion on climate change. During these 24 hours a number of interesting and interactive presentations were held, while all participants had to discuss and come up with innovative and feasible solutions to address climate change challenges. The members of the STEP team not only presented the STEP project, but also participated in the event as mentors providing the participants with information on how e-participation tools could be used by the authorities in order to inspire behavioral change for environmental friendly cities.

- 1st CATCH-EyoU Conference: Athens 2-4 March, 2017

Through the joint contribution of different disciplines (e.g., psychology, education, political science, sociology, media and communications) the first open conference of CATCH-EyoU aimed to explore the multifaceted factors that influence the different forms of youth active engagement in Europe. Additionally, the conference aimed in offering policy makers and professionals working with young people new instruments and “conceptual lenses” to better understand this generation and bring the EU closer to all its citizens. The STEP team participated in the Conference and presented the project at the session: “DIGITAL PARTICIPATION OF EUROPEAN YOUTH”.

7 Overview of the progress towards the expected results

As already presented in Chapter 3.5-Targets and Metrics, the dissemination impact indicator for the STEP NoI is 1.000 registered individual stakeholders by the end of the project (Month 30). This target was achieved by the Month 18 (November 2017), while today there are 1095 registered individual stakeholders.

This could be assessed as very good progress, since the target initially set is surpassed. However, STEP's NoI will be further enriched with additional stakeholders until the end of the project.

8 Future plans and engagement with the NoI

The main objective of future engagement with the STEP NoI is to maintain communication with the existing and future members of the network, to keep up their interest and continue the interaction with them. Until now member engagement has taken place through individual and mass email exchanges, as well as through online and offline activities. Additional activities to maintain participation and encourage active participation and expansion of the network will take place in the period to come. Such actions include:

- A monthly Newsletter sent to all members of the network in order to keep them informed of general news and progress of the STEP project. The STEP pilots have started, so in every newsletter the dialogues of the STEP pilots will be also presented.
- Increase the use and feeding of the STEP social media accounts
- Webinar: The 2nd STEP Webinar will be organized in Month 28 (September 2017), and it will be open to all interested stakeholders.
- Participation in relevant to relevant events and initiatives

9 Conclusions

To sum up, with the submission of the current deliverable in Month 23 (April 2017), the NoI has been established, since the initial goal of 1.000 members has been achieved since Month 18 (November 2016). Today STEP's NoI counts almost 1100 members from 43 countries. The analysis and discussion on the results provided an in-depth view of the dataset. The STEP team has planned a number of online and offline activities in order to maintain the network, keep its members update on STEP's news and enrich it with additional stakeholders.

ANNEX A – STEP 2nd Newsletter

#2
July 2016

step

newsletter

Editorial

Dear readers,

We are glad to present you the second newsletter of the STEP project, which entered its second year of duration in June. During the first year of the project, the technical, operational and business background for the STEP solution has been assessed and analysed, and we are now at the peak of the main development phase of the platform and its components. All partners' efforts are maximised focusing on:

- delivering an integrated and tested eParticipation platform,
- validating the platform through the successful organisation of the project [pilot schemes](#) in 5 locations with the direct participation of one regional authority, three municipalities and one association of municipalities, which are members of the STEP consortium.

Please spread the word widely, and stay tuned via our [website](#), join us on [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#). We are always looking forward to receiving your comments and feedback.

Enjoy the reading!
The STEP Team

In this issue:

- STEP In a nutshell
- STEP In 1 minute
- Engaging young people through social media
- Putting STEP research into practice
- Project workshops
- Publicity events
- Interesting news

 Horizon 2020
European Union funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493
This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The contents of this publication is the sole responsibility of DRAXIS and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

ANNEX B – STEP 3rd Newsletter

#3

April 2017

step

newsletter

Editorial

Dear friends,
The STEP project has entered the second half of its second year and the pilots have been launched!
STEP Platform is open to youngsters and there are currently dialogues in progress organized by 6 agencies from 4 Countries:

- Italy
- Spain
- Greece
- Turkey

One Regional Authority, four Municipalities, and one Association of Municipalities implement STEP pilots and a number of significant environmental issues have already been uploaded at the STEP platform.
Spread the word, stay tuned & enjoy reading!
The STEP team

In this issue:

- A quick glimpse at STEP Platform
- Introducing the STEP pilots
- Introducing STEP at the ENVI Committee
- The STEP blog
- 1st STEP Webinar
- Interesting News & Projects

 Horizon 2020
European Union funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493.
This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The contents of this publication is the sole responsibility of DRAXIS and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

ANNEX C – STEP 1st Webinar

1 s t W e b i n a r

Let's talk about e-participation!

When? Tuesday 14 March 11am (CET)

Three European projects about - e-participation, STEP, EMPATIA and EUth will e-meet at a unique webinar on Tuesday, 14 of March 2017, at 11 am (CET).

STEP: The interactive platform enabling youth Societal and Political e-Participation in decision-making procedures concerning environmental issues.

EMPATIA: The first hands-on digital platform for creating and managing a coherent participatory system that integrates multiple channels of engagement in a single solution.

EUth: The European project that has developed OPIN solution: an all-in-one digital and mobile participation toolbox, which can be embedded in the web presence of youth organisations or public administrations.

Who can Join?

We welcome youth workers, participation experts, software developers, employees in user organizations, or any other party interested in digital participation.

SUBSCRIBE HERE TO JOIN!
<https://goo.gl/forms/lfFYfM1orhceiSuZ2>

 11:00-11:45: What will you learn if you join the webinar:
Welcome / Introduction
Christodoulos Keratidis, Project Manager, STEP project

What is the STEP platform, how it works and what are the partners' future plans
Maria Vogiatzi, Dissemination Manager, STEP Project

The tools and solutions that have been developed in the framework of the EMPATIA project
Michelangelo Secchi, Scientific Coordinator, H2020 EMPATIA Project
Kalinca Copello, Researcher, H2020 EMPATIA Project

What has been achieved so far in the EUth project - the second launch of the OPIN.me platform
Evaldas Rupkus, Project Manager for Marketing, EUth Project

 11:45-12:15: Any questions?
Interactive discussion

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493